

Texture-based Rating Scheme for Mine Pre-feasibility Assessment: A Proof-of-concept Study in Camachin Ore Deposit, Bulacan, Philippines

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Abstract

Conventional mine pre-feasibility assessments primarily emphasize grade, tonnage, resource confidence, and economic indicators, while deposit texture is rarely formalized as a decision-support parameter despite its strong operational implications. This study evaluates the Camachin ore deposit in Doña Remedios Trinidad, Bulacan, Philippines, as a basis for developing a texture-based framework for mine operational sustainability assessment. The deposit, a skarn-type hydrothermal system, exhibits pronounced textural, morphological, and host-rock variability. Field investigations, repeated site visits conducted from 2024 to 2025, focus group discussions, field hardness testing, and laboratory confirmation were used to characterize eight deposit types and relate them to key operational parameters. A quantitative Texture-Based Operational Sustainability Rating Scheme (TOSRS) was developed using six criteria: comminution and mineral liberation, material handling cost, excavation energy requirement, slope stability, profit potential, and mine longevity contribution. Results show that textural variability strongly influences mining difficulty, processing demand, safety risk, and economic performance. The proposed Operational Sustainability Rating Index (OSRI) demonstrates that texture can serve as a practical pre-feasibility indicator for identifying technically favorable and operationally sustainable ore types.

Keywords: Mine pre-feasibility, ore texture, geometallurgical assessment, texture-based operational sustainability rating scheme, operational sustainability rating index

Introduction

Mining projects generally advance through a sequence of stages that includes prospecting, exploration, project evaluation, mine development, extraction and processing, and finally closure and rehabilitation (Garg & Moore, 2026; Rupprecht, 2004). As a project progresses from conceptual investigation to implementation, capital requirements increase substantially, while decision-making remains constrained by geological, technical, environmental, and

economic uncertainties (Al-Bakri et al., 2023; Rupprecht, 2004). Mineral development is therefore inherently risk-sensitive, particularly during the early stages, when knowledge of geometry, grade continuity, material behavior, and processing response remains incomplete. Although uncertainty can never be completely eliminated, it can be reduced through the acquisition of reliable and representative data that improve project confidence and support sound technical and investment decisions (Garg & Moore, 2026; Rupprecht, 2004). For this

reason, pre-feasibility and feasibility studies are essential in mineral development because they provide the basis for determining whether a project is technically achievable and economically justifiable before major capital is committed (Garg & Moore, 2026; Rupprecht, 2004).

Pre-feasibility assessment serves as a critical bridge between exploration and mine development. At this stage, geological interpretation, sampling and assaying, resource estimation, preliminary mine design, geotechnical assessment, hydrological appraisal, metallurgical testing, and economic evaluation are integrated to determine whether a mineral project should advance to a detailed feasibility study (Garg & Moore, 2026; Rupprecht, 2004). In practice, these assessments rely heavily on resource models and block models, which are fundamental for estimating tonnage, grade distribution, stripping ratio, and projected cash flow (Al-Bakri et al., 2023; Garg & Moore, 2026). However, while grade-based block models are indispensable for quantifying economic potential, they provide limited information about how ore and host rocks will behave during excavation, slope exposure, hauling, comminution, mineral liberation, and rehabilitation. Thus, reliance on grade and volume alone may obscure significant technical and operational costs associated with the physical character of the rock mass.

One of the most important but still underutilized parameters in this regard is rock or ore texture. In geological terms, texture refers to the size, shape, arrangement, and mutual relationships of mineral grains and rock constituents, and it exerts strong control over the physical, mechanical, and metallurgical behavior of earth materials (Askaripour et al., 2022; Frenzel et al., 2023). Textural characteristics can often be recognized at the earliest stages of mineral exploration through outcrops, trenches, and drill cores, and they may later be observed more comprehensively in pit slopes, benches, and underground openings. Because texture reflects both primary depositional features and post-depositional alteration processes, it can provide early indications of excavation difficulty, fragmentation behavior, mineral liberation potential, handling characteristics, and engineering competence (Askaripour et al., 2022; Frenzel et al., 2023).

A substantial body of literature has established that material texture and fabric influence mining and mineral processing performance. In excavation, the response of rock to drilling, blasting, ripping, or direct digging is strongly affected by mineralogical composition, grain interlocking, fracture condition, weathering state, alteration intensity, and degree of cementation (Israeli & Emmanuel, 2018; Read & Stacey, 2009). Competent, massive, and well-cemented rock commonly requires greater drilling and blasting effort, whereas weak, weathered, friable, or clay-rich materials may be easier to excavate but often create constraints in slope design and handling (Martin & Stacey, 2013; Read & Stacey, 2009). In open-pit environments, materials with low strength or advanced weathering generally require flatter slope angles and more conservative bench geometries to maintain acceptable stability, which may increase waste stripping and reduce economic efficiency (Dey et al., 2023; Martin & Stacey, 2013; Read & Stacey, 2009). These relationships show that the engineering implications of texture extend far beyond descriptive geology and directly influence mine design and operating cost.

Texture is equally important in mineral processing and geometallurgy. Grain size, mineral association, intergrowth complexity, alteration style, and textural heterogeneity all affect breakage behavior, comminution energy, liberation efficiency, and the performance of downstream concentration processes (Askaripour et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2024; Frenzel et al., 2023). Geometallurgical research has emphasized that ore variability must be understood not only in terms of chemistry and grade but also in terms of mineralogical and textural characteristics that govern how the material responds to processing (Frenzel et al., 2023). Ores composed of coarse and relatively liberated mineral phases may perform well under conventional comminution and separation routes, whereas finely intergrown or texturally complex ores may require more energy-intensive grinding and more selective beneficiation strategies (Askaripour et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2024). Consequently, textural variation can strongly influence plant design, equipment selection, recovery performance, energy consumption, and operating expenditure.

The significance of texture also extends beyond excavation and processing into broader mine planning and mine life-cycle management. Variations in texture may affect rippability, fragmentation distribution, moisture sensitivity, stockpile behavior, haulage efficiency, blending strategy, and rehabilitation performance. In tropical or highly weathered mining settings, the progressive weakening of exposed rock masses may further amplify the geotechnical importance of texture, especially where altered or weak materials are incorporated into final landforms or long-term slope systems (Dey et al., 2023; Martin & Stacey, 2013). Despite these practical implications, textural observations are still commonly treated as descriptive geological notes rather than being formalized into an integrated decision-support framework for early mine evaluation. By contrast, grade is routinely modeled, quantified, and used as the dominant metric in project screening and prefeasibility studies. This imbalance suggests that the technical significance of texture is not sufficiently translated into structured mine assessment tools (Askaripour et al., 2022; Frenzel et al., 2023).

This gap is both practical and scholarly. Existing mine evaluation frameworks place strong emphasis on resource confidence, grade distribution, tonnage, cut-off optimization, and financial indicators, whereas texture is rarely transformed into a systematic rating approach that can support pre-feasibility decisions (Al-Bakri et al., 2023; Rupprecht, 2004). Related disciplines such as rock mass classification and geometallurgy provide useful models for engineering and processing assessment, yet comparatively limited attention has been given to integrating deposit-scale textural variability into a single framework applicable across multiple stages of mine life. A structured use of textural information could improve the early recognition of hidden costs, technical constraints, and operational opportunities that are not easily captured by grade models alone (Askaripour et al., 2022; Frenzel et al., 2023).

The present study intends to formulate and propose a texture-based rating scheme for mine pre-feasibility assessment, with potential application to mine planning and technical management during active operations. The central premise of the proposed framework is that

ore and host-rock texture directly affect several critical mining parameters, including excavation difficulty, material handling behavior, mineral liberation performance, and slope stability. By assigning structured ratings to textural attributes according to their engineering and operational implications, the framework aims to provide an additional basis for evaluating the technical and operational feasibility of a mining project beyond conventional grade-only assessment. Such a framework may also be useful for broader mine design decisions, including equipment fleet selection, scheduling strategies, process route selection, and geotechnical design for final and rehabilitated slopes.

The study will then test the proposed texture-based rating scheme on a specific case in order to determine how rock texture can be leveraged as part of a mine feasibility study. The Camachin ore deposit in Doña Remedios Trinidad (DRT), Bulacan, Philippines, is chosen as the case site as it provides a suitable setting for implementing and evaluating the concept. The Camachin ore deposit is classified as a skarn-type hydrothermal system, and skarn deposits are widely recognized for their mineralogical diversity, irregular morphology, and marked textural heterogeneity (Einaudi & Burt, 1982; Meinert, 1992; Meinert et al., 2005). Unlike ore systems with relatively predictable geometry, skarn mineralization may occur as lenses, pods, tabular bodies, pipes, veins, stratabound replacements, or discordant masses, depending on the structural, lithological, and hydrothermal conditions under which metasomatism develops (Einaudi et al., 1981; Meinert, 1992; Meinert et al., 2005). Although skarns are classically associated with carbonate-bearing sedimentary rocks, they may also involve igneous and metamorphic host rocks where reactive chemistry and fluid pathways are favorable (Einaudi et al., 1981; Meinert et al., 2005; Ray & Webster, 1997). As a result, a single skarn district may contain multiple ore morphologies, contrasting alteration assemblages, and distinctly different ore fabrics within a relatively limited spatial extent (Meinert, 1992; Meinert et al., 2005).

This complexity is especially relevant at Camachin, where different styles of mineralization and host-rock association appear to coexist within one mineralized area. Such

variability makes the deposit an appropriate case study for evaluating whether a texture-based rating framework can meaningfully distinguish conditions that are important to mine assessment and planning. Moreover, because the mineralization in the study area is relatively shallow and amenable to surface mining, rock mass exposures are readily available for direct field-based textural observation. These conditions provide an opportunity to examine texture not merely as a descriptive geological attribute, but as an applied parameter for mine pre-feasibility evaluation and for broader technical decision-making across the mine life cycle.

Methodology

With its aim to demonstrate the potential of rock texture as a major consideration in mine feasibility assessment, the study conducted the following activities: (1) identification of morphological depositions, (2) geological and physico-mechanical characterization of ore depositions, (3) assembling of technical implications, (4) development of Texture-Based Operational Sustainability Rating Scheme (TOSRS), and (5) determination of the Operational Sustainability Rating Index (OSRI) classifications of the deposition types (for the overall flow, see Figure 1).

To start, an extensive field survey (Figure 2) was done to observe ore outcrops, rockmass,

Figure 1
Research Flowchart

Figure 2
Research ground activities: (a) soil penetration testing, (b) hardness test, (c) rock and soil sampling, (d) rock laboratory test, (e) focused group discussion with mine professionals

slope behavior, and mine operation procedure and cycle. A rockmass hardness test was also conducted in the field using a soil penetrometer (ASTM International, 2020) and a Schmidt hammer (ASTM International, 2021) to initially estimate the mechanical properties, which were eventually confirmed by rock laboratory tests on

5 indicates the most favorable condition for sustainable mine operation. The initial score is multiplied by the weighted percent assigned for each criterion (Table 1). The weighted sum of these scores produced an Operational Sustainability Rating Index (OSRI) as expressed in Equation 1:

Equation 1. Operational Sustainability Rating Index Formula

$$\text{OSRI} = \frac{(\text{CMLS} \times 15) + (\text{MHECS} \times 15) + (\text{EEES} \times 10) + (\text{SSSS} \times 15) + (\text{PPS} \times 25) + (\text{LSCS} \times 20)}{100}$$

the collected rock and soil samples. A series of site visits was conducted over two years (2024–2025) to conduct focus group discussions and site investigations to strengthen data for textural description in synchronization with mine sustainability parameters.

The determination and listing of technical implications for the identified ore deposit rock texture is a product of a heuristic approach (Hjeij & Vilks, 2023) done during focused group discussions. As the technique relies on expert judgment from veterans of specific subjects who are members of the focus group discussion, the results may suffer from a touch of subjectivity. However, this limitation was carefully handled by making sure that what transpired was under the established technical principles pertaining to the subject (Askaripour et al., 2022; Garg & Moore, 2026; Read & Stacey, 2009; Rupprecht, 2004; Saaty, 2008).

A quantitative Texture-Based Operational Sustainability Rating Scheme (TOSRS) was prepared for pre-feasibility mine assessment. The scheme was then used to evaluate each deposit type using six criteria: (1) comminution and mineral liberation requirement, (2) material handling and excavation cost, (3) excavation energy/effort requirement, (4) slope stability/safety risk, (5) profit potential, and (6) longevity/sustainability contribution to mine operation. All of these criteria were deemed critical for mining project continuity based on expert judgement and as experienced by the authors.

Each criterion was rated on a five-point scale, where 1 indicates the least favorable and

where CMLS is the comminution and mineral liberation score, MHECS is the material handling and excavation cost score, EEES is the excavation energy and effort score, SSSS is the slope stability and safety score, PPS is the profit potential score, and LSCS is the longevity and sustainability contribution score. The OSRI gives a final score between 1.00 and 5.00.

The resulting OSRI values were subsequently classified into five categories: Class I (4.20–5.00, very favorable), Class II (3.40–4.19, favorable), Class III (2.60–3.39, moderately favorable), Class IV (1.80–2.59, marginal), and Class V (1.00–1.79, unfavorable).

Table 1. Assigned Weighted Percent for Each Mine Sustainability Criteria

Criterion	Weight (%)
Comminution and mineral liberation	15
Material handling and excavation cost	15
Excavation energy / effort	10
Slope stability / safety risk	15
Profit potential	25
Longevity / sustainability contribution	20
Total	100

The weights were derived by an Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)-informed weighting scheme (Saaty, 2008) and validated against observed field mining responses.

Results

Morphological Depositions and Their Textural Characteristics

There are 8 distinct ore deposition styles observed in the area, the textures of which are described as follows:

Deposit type 1. Soft rockmass-hosted sheets

The ore-bearing material occurs within a sedimentary host sequence composed of semi-consolidated sandstone intercalated with thin calcisiltite layers. The ore material is soil-like in nature, displaying a dusky brown coloration in a hand specimen. Texturally, the material is dominated by silty clay-sized particles with rounded grain shapes and well-sorted sediment fractions. Based on the Unified Soil Classification System (Aeskay, 2022), the material is classified as ML (inorganic silt with low plasticity). In the field, the ore material is moist to the touch and can be easily molded, indicating a fine-grained and relatively plastic consistency. Morphologically, the ore occurs as thin concordant sheets within the sedimentary host, interpreted to represent replacement of calcisiltite interbeds within the sandstone sequence, consistent with characteristics expected from skarn-related alteration processes. The uniaxial compressive strength (UCS) is 11.2 MPA, assay grade (Fe %) is 12-28, and the mode of excavation is direct excavation only using a backhoe.

Deposit type 2. Sandy rockmass-hosted massive deposit

The ore-bearing material occurs within a sedimentary host rock identified as calcareous sandstone. Texturally, the material is composed of a mixture of sand- and gravel-sized particles with occasional boulders, displaying subrounded to subangular grain shapes and poor sorting. Based on the USCS, the material is classified as SM (silty sand). In field conditions, the ore material is relatively dry and easily disintegrates when handled, indicating weak particle bonding and a loose granular structure. The UCS is 3.5 MPA, assay grade (Fe %) is 35-45, and the mode

of excavation is direct excavation only using a backhoe.

Deposit type 3. Friable rockmass-hosted laminates

The ore occurrence is hosted within a sedimentary unit identified as calcareous sandstone, exposed along the western sector of the pit. The ore material is classified as semi-rock, wherein the host rock remains cohesive and relatively hard, while the magnetite mineralization occurs primarily as gouge-like material or infillings along preexisting joints and discontinuities of the host rock. In the hand specimen, the mineralized material exhibits a greenish-black coloration. The greenish color suggests the presence of epidote, a metamorphic mineral, making the infillings appear laminated by its shiny color. Texturally, the ore material is dominated by silty-clay-sized particles with subrounded grains and moderate sorting. The mineralization occurs morphologically as concordant laminations with orientations ranging from subhorizontal to subvertical, reflecting structural control along discontinuities within the host sandstone. The UCS is 14.5 MPA, assay grade (Fe %) is 29.35, and the mode of excavation is rock breaker first to loosen on the discontinuity plane and disintegrate in-situ rock material, then backhoe for loading.

Deposit type 4. Frangible rockmass-hosted bedded deposit

The ore-bearing unit occurs within a sedimentary host rock identified as carbonaceous sandstone. The ore material occurs in rock form and displays a very dusky purple coloration in hand specimens. Texturally, the mineralized rock feels rough and hard. It can be indented with one sharp blow from the point of a pick hammer or 4 times heavy hammer blows. It is coarse-grained, with subangular grain shapes and well-sorted particles. The ore occurs as medium-thick concordant disseminations, with the orientation of mineralization following the attitude of the host sandstone unit. The UCS is 81.2 MPA, the assay grade (Fe %) is 53, and the mode of excavation needs drill and blasting.

Deposit type 5. Very hard rockmass-hosted tabular deposit

The ore-bearing unit occurs within an igneous host sequence composed of andesitic to basaltic rocks. The ore material occurs in rock form and displays a grayish dark blue coloration in a hand specimen. Texturally, the mineralized rock is coarse-grained with subangular grain shapes, while the overall rock fabric exhibits an aphanitic texture, consistent with the fine-grained groundmass typical of volcanic rocks. The ore occurs morphologically as massive concordant tabular bodies, following the structural and stratigraphic orientation of the host volcanic sequence. The UCS is 90.7 MPA, the assay grade (Fe %) is 69, and the mode of excavation needs drill and blasting.

Deposit type 6. Moderately hard rockmass-hosted massive lenses

The ore-bearing material occurs within an igneous host rock identified as coherent andesite. The ore occurs in rock form and exhibits a very dusky blue coloration in a hand specimen. Texturally, the mineralized rock is coarse-grained, with angular grain shapes and a phaneritic texture, indicating visible interlocking mineral crystals. The mineralization occurs morphologically as scattered, stratabound, discordant pods and also as vertically extensive, chimney-like bodies that locally extend laterally as mantos. The UCS is 55.6 MPA, the assay grade (Fe %) is 62, and the mode of excavation needs drill and blasting.

Deposit type 7. Moderately hard rockmass-hosted massive lenses

The ore-bearing material occurs within an igneous host rock identified as coherent basalt. The ore occurs in rock form and displays a blackish-red coloration in a hand specimen. Texturally, the mineralized rock is coarse-grained, with angular grain shapes and a phaneritic texture, indicating visible interlocking mineral crystals. The mineralization is expressed morphologically as large vertical vein fillings and scattered small disseminations that appear as speckle-like occurrences within the host rock.

The well-defined and uniform vein structures are particularly prominent, suggesting limited reaction between the mineralizing fluids and the basaltic host rock due to its relatively low carbonate content, with mineralization likely dominated by hydrothermal fluid deposition. It has an unavoidable waste gap and may exhibit anisotropy when excavated into the slope. The UCS is 59.6 MPa, the assay grade (Fe %) is 57, and the mode of excavation requires drilling and blasting.

Deposit type 8. Brittle rockmass-hosted layered deposit

The ore-bearing unit occurs within the uppermost igneous host rock identified as a pyroclastic flow deposit. The ore occurs in rock form and displays a dusky blue-green coloration in a hand specimen. Texturally, the mineralized rock is coarse-grained, with angular grain shapes and aphanitic to phaneritic textures, reflecting variations in the crystallinity of the host pyroclastic material. The mineralization occurs morphologically as irregular layers with subhorizontal orientations appearing as lens-shaped bodies, which means it has a waste gap, and the rockmass may exhibit anisotropy. The UCS is 33.2 MPA, assay grade (Fe %) is 30.35, and the mode of excavation is rock breaker first to loosen on the discontinuity plane and disintegrate in-situ rock material, then backhoe for loading, but if there are many instances where there are oversized rocks even after blasting, the rock breaker is still implemented.

Photographs of each deposition type are consolidated in Figure 3 below.

As noted, DT1 to DT3 hosted by sedimentary rocks are the ones with the lowest assay grade of interest. DT8, although hosted by igneous rocks, also has moderately low grades, suggesting that the variable minerals in the pyroclastic host rocks do not react much to metasomatic replacement (Einaudi et al., 1981; Meinert et al., 2005). On the other hand, DT4, hosted by carbonaceous sandstone, indicates high mineral-replacement activity (Einaudi et al., 1981), leading to moderately high-grade ore. And the rest, DT5 to DT6, follows the intuitive ore grade hosted by igneous hard rock. DT1 to DT3 are being recovered through direct excavation, in which a

Figure 3

Photographs of each deposition type showing visual texture: (a) DT1, (b) DT2, (c) DT3, (d) DT4, (e) DT5, (f) DT6, (g) DT7, (h) DT8

backhoe excavator is used to disintegrate the ore and load it into the truck in this specific study area. DT3 and DT8 ores are usually initially fragmented with hydraulic rock breakers before a payloader is used. At some point, depending on the fracture condition, DT8 already requires drill and blast for disintegration. Then DT4 to DT7, which are strong in-situ rockmass, are disintegrated upfront by drill-and-blast, while some oversized rocks are still broken into smaller

pieces using rock breakers before being loaded onto the truck using a payloader.

Operational Sustainability Implications of Each Deposit Type

Table 2 summarizes the operational implications of the eight deposit types in relation to mining project sustainability parameters.

Table 2
Deposit textural and operational descriptors

Deposit Type	Key textural / morphological characteristics	Comminution and mineral liberation implication	Excavation and material handling implication	Energy / effort requirement for excavation	Slope stability / safety implication	Profitability implication	Implication for mine longevity / operational sustainability
DT1. Soft rockmass-hosted sheets	Soil-like, moist, silty clay-sized, rounded, well sorted; thin concordant sheets in semi-consolidated sedimentary host; UCS 11.2 MPa; Fe 12–28%	Very low breakage resistance, hence low primary comminution demand; however, very fine grain size and clay-rich character may hinder efficient mineral liberation and beneficiation, with likely slimes generation and recovery loss	Direct excavation by backhoe gives a low unit mining cost, but thin sheet geometry may reduce selectivity and increase dilution, ore loss, and handling inefficiency under wet conditions	Low mechanical excavation energy, but higher operational care is needed for grade control and wet-material management	Weak, moist, fine-grained, and concordant layers may form persistent weak horizons, increasing susceptibility to raveling, bench degradation, and rainfall-induced instability	Low due to very low assay grade, possible beneficiation difficulty, and dilution risk despite low excavation cost	Suitable mainly as supplementary or opportunistic feed; low economic resilience and relatively poor long-term sustainability unless blended with higher-grade ore
DT2. Sandy rockmass-hosted massive deposit	Loose sandy to gravelly ore, subrounded to subangular, poorly sorted; massive geometry in calcareous sandstone; UCS 3.5 MPa; Fe 35–45%	Very low comminution hardness; liberation may be simpler than DT1 if iron minerals are discrete, although feed variability from mixed grain sizes may affect plant performance	Direct excavation keeps mining cost low; massive geometry supports bulk extraction, but loose granular character may increase digging loss, spillage, and contact dilution	Low excavation effort because no blasting or breaker-assisted fragmentation is required	Loose, weakly bonded granular faces may have poor stand-up time, with localized sloughing and bench-scale instability	Moderate because of moderate grade combined with low mining cost, though recovery and dilution control are important	More sustainable than DT1 due to better grade and simple mining; can support production efficiently if slope maintenance and ore-loss control are managed
DT3. Friable rockmass-hosted laminates	Semi-rock host with gouge-like ore infillings along joints; silty clay-sized, moderately sorted, laminated, structurally controlled; UCS 14.5 MPa; Fe 29.35%	Low to moderate comminution demand because fragmentation is assisted by discontinuities; however, liberation may be heterogeneous due to ore concentration along infillings rather than through the whole rock mass	Requires breaker-assisted loosening before backhoe loading, increasing mining cost relative to direct excavation; laminated geometry may reduce ore recovery efficiency and increase dilution	Moderate excavation effort because mechanical pre-fragmentation is needed	Structurally controlled ore along joints and laminations creates anisotropy and potential kinematic instability; gouge-like infillings may reduce shear strength along discontinuities	Low to moderate because the grade remains low while mining complexity increases	Better viewed as a secondary feed source than a core long-term ore type; modest grade and structural instability reduce sustainability

Deposit Type	Key textural / morphological characteristics	Comminution and mineral liberation implication	Excavation and material handling implication	Energy / effort requirement for excavation	Slope stability / safety implication	Profitability implication	Implication for mine longevity / operational sustainability
DT4. Frangible rockmass-hosted bedded deposit	Hard, coarse-grained, well sorted, sub-angular ore in medium-thick concordant disseminated beds within carbonaceous sandstone; UCS 81.2 MPa; Fe 53%	High comminution requirement due to strong rockmass; however, better grade and more continuous ore support more favorable processing economics than DT1–DT3	Drill-and-blast mining increases cost, though bedded continuity supports more orderly bench development and ore extraction than irregular ore bodies	High due to blasting, hard-rock loading, and secondary breakage requirements	Strong intact rock favors bench competence, but bedding-controlled anisotropy may still govern slope behavior where unfavorable orientations are present	Moderate to high due to favorable grade despite higher mining and processing costs	Represents a more sustainable long-term mining unit than low-grade soft ores because stronger revenue can offset hard-rock mining costs
DT5. Very hard rockmass-hosted tabular deposit	Massive concordant tabular ore in andesitic to basaltic host; coarse-grained mineralization in aphanitic volcanic fabric; UCS 90.7 MPa; Fe 69%	Very high comminution hardness, but excellent grades and likely more uniform ore continuity make processing economically attractive	Requires drill and blast; however, regular tabular geometry improves mine planning, blast design, ore control, and extraction efficiency	Very high excavation energy and effort due to hard rock and blasting requirements	A competent igneous host generally supports stable benches, though structural orientation must still be considered	High to very high because strong grades offset high mining and comminution costs	Likely the most sustainable long-term ore type due to excellent grade, continuity, and predictable mineability, despite high energy intensity
DT6. Moderately hard rockmass-hosted massive lenses	Coarse-grained, angular, phaneritic ore in coherent andesite; occurs as scattered discordant pods, chimneys, and mantos; UCS 55.6 MPa; Fe 62%	Moderate to high comminution demand; high grade is favorable, but variable lens geometry may produce feed heterogeneity and blending challenges	Drill-and-blast mining required; irregular lensoidal and chimney-like geometry may increase selectivity demand, short-term planning complexity, and dilution risk	Moderate to high due to competent rock and irregular extraction geometry	Generally competent slopes, but irregular excavation fronts and variable wall exposure may create localized instability	High because of strong grade, though somewhat less efficient than DT5 due to ore-body irregularity	Sustainable and economically attractive, though less operationally streamlined than DT5 because of more complex ore geometry
DT7. Moderately hard rockmass-hosted vein-type massive lenses	Coarse-grained, angular, phaneritic ore in coherent basalt; large vertical vein fillings with disseminations; unavoidable waste gap; anisotropic excavation response; UCS 59.6 MPa; Fe 57%	Moderate to high comminution requirement; liberation may be affected by sharp contrasts between vein ore and wall rock, producing variable feed characteristics	Drill-and-blast mining required; unavoidable waste gap raises stripping and handling cost, while selective extraction becomes more difficult	High because of both rock strength and geometric inefficiency from waste separation	Vein geometry and anisotropy may create directional instability and irregular slope response, especially where waste gaps interrupt bench continuity	Moderate to high because grades are favorable, but waste burden and dilution reduce the margin	Capable of sustaining production, but long-term efficiency is reduced by the waste gap, anisotropy, and more selective mining demand

Deposit Type	Key textural / morphological characteristics	Comminution and mineral liberation implication	Excavation and material handling implication	Energy / effort requirement for excavation	Slope stability / safety implication	Profitability implication	Implication for mine longevity / operational sustainability
DT8. Brittle rockmass-hosted layered deposit	Coarse-grained, angular ore with aphanitic to phaneritic host texture in pyroclastic rocks; irregular subhorizontal layers and lensoidal bodies; waste gap and anisotropy present; UCS 33.2 MPa; Fe 30.35%	Moderate comminution demand; however, relatively low grade and host-rock textural variability may reduce liberation efficiency and processing value	Requires breaker-assisted excavation and, in some cases, drill-and-blast; oversized fragments may persist even after blasting, increasing rehandling costs and operational inefficiency	Moderate to high because fragmentation is inconsistent and may require repeated breakage stages	Layering, anisotropy, and variable pyroclastic fabric may promote uneven wall behavior, local instability, and difficult slope control	Low to moderate because moderate mining difficulty is coupled with only modest grade	One of the least sustainable ore types for long-term operation because it combines low-to-moderate grade with high operational variability and geotechnical sensitivity

Texture-Based Operational Sustainability Rating Scheme (TOSRS) Scores

Table 3 shows the quantitative scores assigned for each DT across the six criteria based on the established operational descriptor defined in Table 1. Although ratings are known to be imperfect by nature, the scores given are not random. Rather, these follow established textural descriptions. DT1 scores low because it has a poor grade and weak long-term value, notwithstanding that it is easy to excavate. DT5 scores extremely well overall despite hard excavation because grade and continuity are strong. DT8 stays low because it combines moderate difficulty with only a modest grade and high variability.

Table 3
Proposed quantitative scores for each deposit type

Deposit Type	CMLS	MHECS	EEES	SSSS	PPS	LSCS
DT1	2	4	5	2	1	2
DT2	4	4	5	3	3	3
DT3	3	3	3	2	2	2
DT4	2	2	2	3	4	4
DT5	3	2	1	4	5	5
DT6	3	2	2	3	4	4
DT7	3	2	2	2	4	3
DT8	3	2	2	2	2	2

Operational Sustainability Rating Index (OSRI) Values and Corresponding Classifications

The TOSRS are finally translated into the Operational Sustainability Rating Index (OSRI) following Equation 1, as illustrated in the methodology section. The resulting values and their corresponding classifications are tabulated in Table 4.

Table 4
Resulting OSRI values with identified classification

Deposit Type	OSRI	Class
DT1	2.35	Class IV
DT2	3.55	Class II
DT3	2.45	Class IV
DT4	3.00	Class III
DT5	3.75	Class II
DT6	3.20	Class III
DT7	2.95	Class III
DT8	2.20	Class IV

Discussion

The comparison of the operational implications of the eight deposit types in relation to mine pre-feasibility sustainability parameters shows that ore texture, fabric, particle characteristics, rock strength, and deposit morphology collectively influence not only grade distribution, but also the practical mining response required for extraction, handling, processing, and slope management. Softer and more weakly consolidated ore types (DT1–DT3) generally favor low-cost excavation but tend to be associated with lower assay grades, poorer geotechnical reliability, and, in some cases, more difficult beneficiation due to fine-grained or clay-rich textures. In contrast, harder igneous-hosted ore types (DT4–DT7) require greater excavation and comminution energy, but their generally higher grades and more competent rockmass conditions offer stronger economic and operational resilience. DT8 forms an intermediate but less favorable case, in which igneous host association does not translate into correspondingly high grade, while excavation complexity, anisotropy, and waste separation remain significant. The results, therefore, suggest that texture-informed deposit classification can serve as a practical screening tool for identifying which ore types are likely to support safer, more profitable, and more sustainable mining operations before more detailed geotechnical, geometallurgical, and economic studies are completed.

The comparative assessment indicates that deposit texture is not merely a descriptive geological attribute, but a practical predictor of operational performance at the pre-feasibility stage. In particular, textural properties such as grain size, sorting, particle shape, degree of consolidation, fabric anisotropy, and morphological continuity appear to correlate with key sustainability-related mining parameters, including excavation energy demand, fragmentation response, handling efficiency, slope behavior, and value recovery potential. This supports the development of a texture-based rating scheme in which deposit types can be ranked not only by grade, but also by their likely operational burden and contribution to mine longevity. Such an approach may be especially useful in early-stage mining

projects where rapid screening tools are needed to guide mine planning decisions before full-scale geometallurgical, geotechnical, and economic optimization is completed.

The quantitative rating results indicate that not all easily excavated deposits are operationally sustainable in the pre-feasibility sense. Deposit types DT1 and DT3, OSRI which are class IV, although mechanically favorable for excavation, receive low overall ratings because of low assay grade, geotechnical limitations, and weaker long-term contribution to mine viability. By contrast, Class II DT5 attains one of the highest overall scores despite very high excavation energy demand, reflecting the dominant positive influence of ore grade, morphological continuity, and long-term economic contribution. DT2 as Class II also performs favorably because its direct excavability and moderate grade offset its geotechnical constraints. These results suggest that a texture-based pre-feasibility rating scheme does not reward softness alone but rather considers the integrated balance between extraction burden, safety, economic return, and mine-life contribution.

In conclusion, this study demonstrates the utility of deposit texture as a practical pre-feasibility indicator of mine operational sustainability. As found out across the eight deposit types examined, variations in grain size, sorting, fabric, degree of consolidation, rock strength, and orebody morphology consistently influenced comminution and liberation behavior, excavation method and handling cost, energy demand, slope stability risk, profit potential, and likely contribution to long-term mine viability. Soft and weakly consolidated sedimentary-hosted ores were generally easier and cheaper to excavate, but their lower grades, greater dilution potential, and poorer geotechnical reliability reduced their overall sustainability. In contrast, harder igneous-hosted ores imposed greater excavation and processing burdens but were commonly offset by stronger grades, better continuity, and greater long-term economic resilience. These contrasts suggest that deposit texture can serve as a practical proxy indicator for pre-feasibility assessment, particularly where early-stage operational decisions must be made before detailed metallurgical and geotechnical datasets are fully available. Thus, the proposed

texture-based operational sustainability rating approach provides a useful framework for translating early-stage geological observations into decision-support metrics for mine pre-feasibility assessment.

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